

**CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED AND COPING
STRATEGIES USED BY TEACHERS IN
IMPLEMENTING SPED INCLUSIVE EDUCATION
PROGRAM IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS OF
THIRD CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT, DIVISION OF
QUEZON**

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Challenges Encountered and Coping Strategies Used by Teachers in Implementing SPED Inclusive Education Program in Public Elementary Schools of Third Congressional District, Division of Quezon

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to ascertain the challenges encountered and coping strategies used by teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program in public elementary schools of the third congressional district in the division of Quezon. It also covered the types of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEN), the teaching strategies utilized by teachers, challenges encountered, and the coping strategies used by teachers to address the challenges they encountered. This study used judgment or purposive sampling in choosing eight teachers who implement the SPED inclusive education program in third congressional district of Quezon. This study utilized qualitative research method and structured interview guide in gathering needed information to better understand the challenges encountered and coping strategies that teachers used in implementing SPED inclusive education program. It is revealed in the study that learners with Autism Spectrum Disorders, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), and Dyslexia are the major types of learners with special educational needs that are handled by teachers in SPED inclusive education program. The common teaching strategies that teachers use when they instructing learners are the following: using visual aids, educational videos, positive reinforcement, simplification of the lesson, consistent routines, peer tutoring, giving clear instructions, giving written handouts, reading materials, repeated instructions, giving multiple examples, using individualized learning instructions, cooperative and experimental learning. Majority of the teachers agreed that positive reinforcement is the best teaching strategy in SPED inclusive education program by focusing on strengths, encouraging desired behaviors, and fostering a positive learning environment, teachers can support the holistic development of the learners. When it comes in the challenges, the following: dealing with behavioral problem of the LSEN, communication challenge, lack of parental involvement, lack of materials, and dealing with chronic absenteeism are among the challenges teachers encountered. Furthermore, the coping strategies used by teachers to address the challenges they encountered are the following: using differentiated instructions, having emotional understanding, professional development, positive instructions, being relaxed, seeking assistance and encouragement. Most of the teachers stated that the best coping strategy for dealing with the challenges they faced is having emotional understanding. Based from the results of the study, the researcher developed the intervention program, which is advised to use as a support in better implementing SPED inclusive education programs for learners with special educational needs.

Keywords: *challenges, coping strategies, encountered, inclusive education, SPED*

Introduction

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) discussed inclusive education at its salamanca conference. The salamanca statement on inclusive education is a significant international document in the field of special needs. This means that every learner has a constitutional right to education and should be able to access it. As a result, teaching should take into consideration the diversity of the features and needs of children (Hardy & Woodcock, 2015).

The establishment of inclusive schools is a component of an inclusive society, and inclusion is a basic and universal right. Many nations have actively examined human rights issues, and each nation is responsible for fulfilling the global duty to develop inclusive policy.

The SPED inclusive education concepts, policies, and practices support the most effective ways to forge friendly ties among people, get rid of prejudice, cultivate an inclusive society, and ensure that

everyone has access to quality education. All learners should receive a quality education at inclusive schools, which will increase educational effectiveness and reduce costs. Through their increased participation in education, cultural practices, and community activities, inclusive education aims to understand and respond to the diverse needs of learners while also reducing marginalization inside the classroom.

A lengthy procedure has been used to explain inclusive education. Every kid being fully involved in child-friendly schools and society as a whole is the eventual objective of this ongoing process, which calls for a long-term vision.

According to Barton (2017), inclusive education is more than just giving students who have been previously excluded access to mainstream schools. There are numerous advantages to fully integrating learners with special educational needs into the general education class. It is crucial in ensuring that all kids reach their maximum potential. Growing

evidence that inclusive education benefits students with and without special needs.

Additionally, McMillian (2018), the SPED inclusive education has advantages such as acceptance, improved academic standards, and the eradication of social bias against those with learners with special educational needs. He discovered that learners with special needs are more likely to be socially accepted by their peers when they attend a general education class. According to McCarty (2018), learners with special educational needs can develop their social skills and behavior in inclusive settings by modeling after their classmates. Learners with special needs are socially accepted in general classroom settings. As a result, SPED inclusive education helps kids develop favorable attitudes about accepting their peers who have disabilities.

Furthermore, Nishan (2018), argued that it has always been challenging to include learners with special educational needs in general education classes. There is increasing demand to enrich knowledge in existing educational programs to equip teachers with relevant skills and teaching learning knowledge to provide quality education for all. In a like manner, Schuelka (2014), stated that teachers must appropriately professionalize themselves to teach learners with special educational needs. Indeed, Dapudong (2014), noted that teachers' attitudes and awareness are of great value to the system because those professionals can fill any gaps between formally designed educational programs and their actual delivery in terms of curriculum modification and adaptations that are suitable for learners with special educational needs. One of the main obstacles to inclusive education is a lack of knowledge of the idea of it, as well as a negative attitude toward learners with special educational needs and resistance to change.

With this background context, the researcher tried to evaluate the challenges encountered and coping strategies used by the teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program. This study was conducted in the third congressional district of Quezon.

Research Questions

This study's primary goals were to ascertain and evaluate the challenges encountered and coping strategies used by teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program in public elementary schools of the third congressional district of Quezon province. It specifically sought solutions to the following issues:

1. What types of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEN) are handled by the teacher-respondents in SPED inclusive education program?
2. What are the teaching strategies utilized by teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program in terms of:
 - 2.1. Common teaching strategies;
 - 2.2. Best teaching strategies
3. What are the challenges encountered by the teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program?
4. What are the coping strategies used by teachers to address the challenges they encountered in implementing SPED inclusive education program?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used the qualitative research method. The purpose of qualitative research is frequently to inspire people to share their experiences and tales. The goal of qualitative research is to develop a comprehensive understanding of human behavior and the factors that influence it. Qualitative techniques aim to comprehend the context and environment in which the study's respondents handle the problem.

This qualitative phenomenology study uses a comparative, cross-sectional approach to better understand the challenged encountered and coping strategies used by teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program. Structured in-depth interviews were used as part of the phenomenological methodology. Data collection from participants who are experiencing the phenomenon is necessary for empirical research. According to Creswell (2013), a phenomenological approach to data collection enables the researcher to collect information in environments where participants are experiencing the topic being studied. The researcher investigate the challenges that each respondent has faced and the coping strategy they have employed depending on their responses and the themes that emerged from the literature study.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the third congressional district of Quezon, more commonly known as Bondoc Peninsula. The district is composed of 12 municipalities, namely: Padre Burgos, Agdangan, Unisan, Pitogo, Macalelon, General Luna, Catanauan, Mulanay, San Narciso, San Andres, San Francisco, and Buenavista. It is situated in the western portion of the Bicol area, in the southernmost section of Quezon. There are 213 public primary schools in the area, with central schools located in the municipalities' core towns.

The choice of the research locale was due to the researcher's deep concern of knowing the challenges encountered and coping strategies used by teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education

program in the said district of Quezon concerning various aspects.

Research Population and Sample

The study used judgment or purposive sampling, and the researcher chose a sample that agreed with her subjective judgment of a representative sample. Instead of just selecting any sampling unit that is easy to reach, there is now an attempt to come up with a representative sample. The selection of the sampling units included in the sample does not involve any randomization mechanism so this methods still falls under non-probability sampling. For this study, the researcher select participants who have experience in teaching SPED inclusive education program and teaching learners with special educational needs. The researcher considered selecting participants from all mega schools with SPED centers in the third congressional district of Quezon, namely Catanauan Central School and San Andres Central Elementary School, with a total sample of eight respondents handling SPED inclusive education program.

Research Instrument

The research instrument that was used in gathering the needed information is a structured interview guide. A structured interview is a controlled way to obtain information from interviewees. In other words, it is a pre-planned interview where the researcher writes down the questions before conducting the interview. Such a format is an effective way to keep the interview tightly focused on the target topic. The instruments were administered through face-to-face interviews. The teachers implementing SPED inclusive education program were the participants in the interview. The interview questions gathered relevant information concerning the challenges encountered and coping strategies teachers use in implementing SPED inclusive education program. The qualitative instrument was divided into four parts. The first part determined the types of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEN) handled by teachers. The second part of the instrument determined the teaching strategies utilized by teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program in terms of common and best teaching strategies. The third part identified the challenges encountered in implementing SPED inclusive education program for learners with special educational needs. While the last part determined the coping strategies, teachers used to address the challenges they encountered in implementing SPED inclusive education programs.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher started the data gathering with the preparations and development of the research instrument, then it was subjected to validation. After the validation, the research instrument sample was

submitted to the DepEd Quezon for approval. Before administering the interview, a permission letter for conducting the research was sent to an authorized person for approval. After the approval, the researcher proceeded to the actual data gathering by administering the interview personally to explain the purpose and content of the interview. This protects the responses' reliability, validity, and secrecy. The interview provided in-depth details on the topic under study. An interview with a subject matter expert can give meaningful insights that a generalized public source could not provide. Interviews were conducted in person and treated as professional conversations to get meaningful information about the topic. All conversations were recorded and transcribed.

Results and Discussion

The information the researcher obtained to address the issues raised in the Statement of the Problem (SOP) is presented in this chapter. This information was gathered using the study's qualitative instruments, from which this data was extracted. types of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEN), teaching strategies utilized by the teachers, challenges encountered by the teachers, and coping strategies used by teachers.

Types of Learners with Special Educational Needs to be Handled by the Teacher-Respondents in SPED Inclusive Education Program

Table 1. *Types of Learners with Special Educational Needs*

Questions	Responses	Codes
	Teacher 1: "Difficulty in handling and grasping pencils is the common characteristic of my learner with special education needs in class. He also has a short span of interest and has difficulty in social interaction."	
How do you describe your learners with special educational needs (LSEN) in terms of their physical and mental characteristics?	Teacher 2: The characteristic of my learner with special educational needs is that she gets easily frustrated. She has a short span of interest and quickly gets bored. Moreover, has trouble interacting or playing with her classmates. She has little or brief eye contact with other people."	Autism Spectrum Disorder

Teacher 3: "My LSEN pupil has difficulty of hearing or being deaf, but in terms of physical appearance, he is bigger and taller than his classmates. Moreover, when it comes to mental characteristics, he is showing maturity and proper manner. Compared to his other classmates, I can say that he is much more behaved and most disciplined in class."	Difficulty of Hearing
Teacher 4: "Sometimes my LSEN pupil has irritating or thoughtless behavior. He always wants to quarrel with his classmates. He dislikes participating in activities and has trouble interacting or playing with his classmates."	Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)
Teacher 5: "My learner has difficulty participating with his classmates during group activities because sometimes he is moody, but he can easily understand the lesson we tackled."	
Teacher 6: "I have a learner with a learning difficulty. He has poor reading fluency, poor memory, difficulty in following directions, and short attention span."	
Teacher 7: "My learner cannot follow the simple direction, cannot comprehend the text that she reads, has poor memory, and has a short attention span, that she cannot participate in any discussion."	Dyslexia
Teacher 8: "My learner has handwriting difficulties, wherein he could poorly duplicate letters and words exactly as it is/ they are. There is an interchange in the placement of orders of letters and words. He often misses some of its details in strokes."	Dysgraphia

Table 1 shows the different types of learners with special educational needs handled by the teachers in the SPED inclusive education program. The types of learners with special educational needs that emerged are the following: Autism Spectrum Disorder, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), Difficulty of Hearing, Dyslexia, and Dysgraphia. Among these, Autism Spectrum Disorder, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), and Dyslexia are the major types of learners with special educational needs that are handled by teachers in SPED inclusive education, where respondents stated that:

"The characteristic of my learner with special educational needs is that she gets easily frustrated. She has a short span of interest and easily gets bored. Moreover, she has trouble interacting or playing with her classmates. She has little or brief eye contact with other people." (Teacher 2)

"Sometimes my LSEN pupil has irritating or thoughtless behavior. He always wants to quarrel with his classmates. He dislikes participating in activities and has trouble interacting or playing with his classmates." (Teacher 4)

"My learner cannot follow the simple direction, cannot comprehend the text that she reads, has poor memory, and she has a short attention span, that she cannot participate in any discussion." (Teacher 7)

Various literature and studies have provided different types of learners with special educational needs handled by teachers in SPED inclusive education programs.

According to Mackenzie and Cologon (2016), autism spectrum disorders are persistent, complicated neurological conditions that impair cerebral functioning and can cause issues with communication, behavior, and social interaction. The process of identifying and eliminating obstacles to participation and belonging for young children with autism spectrum disorder can be broadly defined as inclusion.

While Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) affects specific cerebral circuits that are primarily in charge of maintaining attention at all times and avoiding distractions, it is a neurological disorder. Due to many symptoms of ADHD, such as inattention, disruptive and aggressive conduct, and issues with working memory, planning, and organizing, a kid with ADHD may find it challenging to succeed in the classroom. Giving teachers the tools they need to work with ADHD students may boost their self-esteem as educators and their general well-being. The ability to educate children who exhibit symptoms of ADHD and modify classroom management may also be aided by greater information for teachers (Gaastra et al., 2016).

Furthermore, the dyslexia issue with word recognition is connected to the area of the brain that processes phonological and orthographic parts of the language. Dyslexia is a problem with language processing that results from improper intellectual functioning. Additionally, it differs from cognitively associated reading issues. According to Ahmed (2018), it's critical to use efficient teaching techniques while working with dyslexic students. Intercession includes the ability to recognize words, spell them correctly, and read aloud easily.

SPED inclusive education program aims to provide appropriate supports and accommodations to address the individual needs of each learner, fostering their academic growth, social development, and overall well-being. By embracing an inclusive mindset, teachers can create an environment that celebrates diversity, promotes equity, and empowers learners with special educational needs to thrive alongside their peers.

Teaching Strategies Utilized by Teachers in Implementing SPED Inclusive Education Program

Table 2. Common Teaching Strategies Utilized by Teachers

Question	Responses	Codes
What teaching strategies are you utilizing in teaching LSEN?	Teacher 1: "In teaching LSEN, I use different strategies like using visual aids, and educational videos, making lessons simpler, carry out everyday routines consistently because he has a short span of interest. Most of the time, I utilized positive reinforcement for good behavior and the entire task completed."	Visuals aids Educational Videos Simplify the lesson Consistent Routines Positive Reinforcement
	Teacher 2: "I use pictures or visual aids in teaching to get the attention of my LSEN pupil. I simplify our lesson and always use positive reinforcement for positive behavior that my pupil have done."	Visual Aids Simplify the lesson Positive reinforcement
	Teacher 3: "The teaching strategies I use in teaching my LSEN pupils is by providing written handouts and visual aids to ensure a clear line of sight and show captioned educational interpreted videos."	Written Handouts Visual Aids Educational Videos
	Teacher 4: "The teaching strategies I use for my LSEN pupil was giving positive reinforcement when he did a good deed, and adopt the peer tutor technique."	Positive Reinforcement Peer-tutoring
	Teacher 5: "I provide my learners with written copies/handouts, and I give clear instructions or directions orally."	Written Handouts Clear Instructions
	Teacher 6: "I give reading materials with pictures to read by herself."	Reading materials
	Teacher 7: "I used to discuss repeatedly the instructions so he will understand the lesson. I give multiple examples,	Repeated Instructions Multiple examples
	Teacher 8: "Some of the strategies that I have been using are cooperative learning, individualized learning instruction, and experimental learning. These strategies will allow them to learn from their peers, gain learning customized to their ability and experience the actual activity and tasks by letting them do the assigned tasks."	Cooperative Learning Individualized instructions Experimental Learning

Table 2 shows the different teaching strategies that the teachers commonly utilized in teaching learners with special educational needs. The common teaching strategies that emerged are the following: visuals aids, educational videos, positive reinforcement, simplifying the lesson, consistent routines, written handouts, peer-tutoring, giving clear instructions, reading materials, repeated instructions, giving multiple examples, cooperative learning, individualized instructions, and experimental learning. Among these, using positive reinforcement and visual aids are observed to have the most statements, where respondents state that:

"I use pictures or visual aids in teaching to get the attention of my LSEN pupil. I simplify our lesson and always use positive reinforcement for positive behavior that my pupils have done" (Teacher 2)

"The teaching strategies that I use to my LSEN pupils are using positive reinforcement when he did a good deed. And also try to understand his behavior and adopt the peer tutor technique" (Teacher 4)

Various literature and studies have provided different teaching strategies for special educational needs. Positive reinforcement proves to be the most effective way to modify and encourage different behavior in the classroom. Those who believe this reinforcement technique is a peaceful fad will be disappointed. Sometimes people from various generations or with different educational philosophies don't understand the benefits of positive reinforcement. However, more people are beginning to grasp this developing and successful teaching method. A teacher must first encourage positive social connections and assess how well their pupils get along with one another before utilizing positive reinforcement in the classroom (Bowker & Casas, 2016).

According to Antonova et al. (2019), visual images are better retained in our brains than spoken ones. The visual aids engage students and make it simple for teachers to explain subjects. Visual aids are educational tools that support the teaching-learning process in the classroom. Students learn more effectively from words and visuals than from just words.

Table 3. Best Teaching Strategies Utilized by Teachers

Question	Responses	Codes
Which of these strategies do you consider the best for handling LSEN?	Teacher 1: The best strategy for my LSEN was utilizing the educational video-assisted. He always wanted new because of his short pan of interest."	Educational Video
	Teacher 2: "I think the best strategy in handling my LSEN pupil is using positive reinforcement or encouraging the LSEN to participate in class."	Positive Reinforcement
	Teacher 3: "The best strategy I used for my LSEN pupil is through visual learning style, so I supplement verbal lectures with handouts, diagrams or other visual materials."	Visual Materials
	Teacher 4: "The best strategy that I use with my LSEN pupil is through using positive reinforcement than punishment. I use positive reinforcement to encourage him to do good deeds for others."	Positive Reinforcement
	Teacher 5: "Providing my learner with written copies so he can follow on our activity"	Written Copies
	Teacher 6: "Give my pupil a reading materials to enhance her reading ability."	Reading Materials
	Teacher 7: "Repeating instructions in every activity so my pupil can follow in our discussion."	Repeated instructions
	Teacher 8: "Individualized learning instruction worked effectively in handling my LSEN, for they were able to progress in their learning phase. This type of strategy drives the teacher and the learners to provide what fits them and their needs to learn."	Individualized Learning Instruction

Table 4. *Challenges Encountered by the Teachers*

Question	Responses	Codes
What are the challenges encountered by the teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program for learners with special educational needs?	Teacher 1. "The challenge I always encounter in teaching LSEN is the difficulty of disciplining the learner. LSEN sometimes has behavioral issues such as gentleness and moodiness. They also have short attention spans. Most of the time, his classmates imitate his behavior."	behavioral problem
	Teacher 2. "When it comes to teaching my LSEN, I find it difficult to handle her behavior because sometimes she is not following my instructions, or sometimes she just has tantrums or meltdowns."	behavioral problem
	Teacher 3. "I find challenging the using sign language. This might create a communication barrier with my LSEN pupil because I do not have training in the proper use of sign language. My LSEN pupil sometimes relies only on lip reading, so I changed my speaking style. I speak clearly and slowly so he can understand what I am saying."	communication challenge
	Teacher 4. "I experience the problem in handling the behavior of my LSEN pupil like noise making in class."	behavioral problem
	Teacher 5. "Lack of parents' involvement or lack of parental engagement also lack of teaching materials for my LSEN pupil."	lack of parental involvement lack of teaching materials
	Teacher 6. "Minsan pasaway sya sa klase at hindi sya matutukan dahil sa dami ng bata na dipa marunong at mas makulit pa sa kanya"	behavioral problem
	Teacher 7. "I find it difficult in handling his behavior because sometimes he is aggressive."	behavioral problem
	Teacher 8: "My pupil frequently miss classes or consistently absent that's why he struggle in studying and were left in some activities provided for them."	Chronic Absenteeism

Table 3 shows the best teaching strategies that teachers utilized in teaching learners with special educational needs. The teaching strategies that emerged are: educational video, positive reinforcement, visual materials, written copies, reading materials, repeated instructions, and individualized learning instructions. Among these, positive reinforcement is observed to have the most statements that best strategy to use in teaching learners with special educational needs, where respondents stated that:

"I think the best strategy in handling my LSEN pupil is through using positive reinforcement or providing encouragement to the LSEN to participate in class." (Teacher 2)

"The best strategy that I use to my LSEN pupils is through using positive reinforcement than punishment. I use positive reinforcement to encourage him to do good deeds to other people." (Teacher 4)

Different effective teaching tactics that are used in instructing students with special educational needs have been offered by various studies and pieces of literature.

Positive reinforcement is the only strategy teachers employ to promote academic success and self-esteem among kids with learning difficulties, according to Evan and Weiss (2017) great reinforcement can have great impacts on a student, but some teachers mistakenly believe that it only rewards students for behavior that they should be engaging in any way. Positive reinforcement may only be described as such if it makes it more likely that the behavior will recur. The special educators within a school system must be willing to share their knowledge with general educators and creatively facilitate the use of targeted and individualized strategies that promote positive behavior for this positive reinforcement strategy in inclusive classrooms to be successful.

Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in Implementing SPED Inclusive Education Program

Table 4 shows the challenges encountered by the teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program for learners with special educational needs. The challenges that emerged are the following: behavioral problems, communication challenges, lack of parental involvement, lack of teaching materials chronic absenteeism. Among these, it is noted that majority of the teachers encountered behavioral problem in SPED inclusive education program, wherein they stated that:

"The challenge I always encounter in teaching LSEN is the difficulty of disciplining the learner, LSEN sometimes has behavioral issues such as gentleness and moodiness. They also have short attention spans. Most of the time, his classmates imitate his behavior." (Teacher 1)

"When it comes to teaching my LSEN, I find it difficult in handling her behavior because sometimes she is not following my instructions or sometimes she just having tantrums or meltdowns" (Teacher 2)

"I experience the problem in handling the behavior of my LSEN pupil like noise making in class." (Teacher 4)

Behavioral problems among pupils in the implementation of SPED inclusive education programs can pose significant challenges for teachers. These issues can arise due to a variety of factors, including individual learning differences, emotional and social difficulties, and the lack of appropriate support systems. However, it is crucial to approach these problems with empathy, understanding, and effective strategies to create an inclusive and conducive learning environment. Stanford and Rose (2018) noted that several studies have looked at general education pupils who had behavioral problems. According to research, peers distance themselves from hostile students. The current study adds to existing findings by showing that violent actions among students are not the only ones that cause exclusion. It has the same effect on classmates when kids with emotional and behavioral issues brag about their special position in class and take advantage of exceptional circumstances and special treatment to obtain what they believe to be unfair benefits.

Numerous research has shown that kids with emotional and behavioral issues are the ones who are most likely to experience worries, worry, and unfavorable attitudes about inclusion. Teachers must reengage these children while minimizing disturbances and delivering uninterrupted lessons to the rest of the class because they frequently exhibit behaviors like difficulty focusing or being disruptive and upsetting.

Coping Strategies Used by Teachers to Address the Challenges They Encountered in Implementing SPED Inclusive Education Program

Table 5. Coping Strategies Used by Teachers to Address the Challenges They Encountered

Question	Responses	Codes
What coping strategies do you consider as most effective in addressing those encountered challenges?	Teacher 1: "To address the problem, I utilized differentiated instruction wherein the learners are kept busy, and my LSEN pupil became interested in participating."	Differentiated Instructions
	Teacher 2: "To address the challenges I encountered, I just try to understand their emotions, use deep breathing, and have long patience to handle their behavior."	Emotional Understanding
	Teacher 3: "Attending seminars or training sessions about handling LSEN pupils, so I can enrich my knowledge on how to handle them."	Professional Development
	Teacher 4: "The best way that I use to address the problem is by giving my LSEN pupil positive instructions when trying to correct his endless noise-making. Find positive things about them, speak to the pupil calmly, understand their emotions, explain what he must do, and turn hostile to positive behavior."	Positive Instructions Emotional Understanding
	Teacher 5: "In just relax and I do not allow myself to be pressured."	Being Relax
	Teacher 6: "Seeking support or assistance from the professional expert who handle LSEN."	Seeking Assistance
	Teacher 7: "Letting his classmate by treating him as they are, understanding his behavior and encouraging him to participate in a group activity, guiding him on dos and don'ts of being a learner."	Encouragement Emotional understanding
	Teacher 8: "Addressing the encountered challenges can be possibly realized by getting assistance and help from their peers and seatmates wherein learning took place through peer tutoring."	Seeking Assistance

Table 5 shows the coping strategies used by the teachers in addressing their challenges. The teachers reported that the coping strategies that they use are the following: differentiated instructions, having emotional understanding, professional development, positive instructions, being relax, seeking assistance and encouragement.

Based on the responses of the teachers, having emotional understanding is the major coping strategies they use to address their challenges, wherein they stated that :

"To address the challenges that I encountered, I just try to understand their emotions, I use deep breathing, and have long patience to handle their behavior." (Teacher 2)

"The best way that I use to address the problem is by giving my LSEN pupil positive instructions when trying to correct his endless noise making. Find positive things about them, speak to the pupil calmly, understand their emotions, explain what he must do, and turn hostile to positive behavior." (Teacher 4)

"Letting his classmate by treating him as same as they are; understand his behavior and encouraging him to participate in a group activity, guiding him on dos and don'ts of being a learner" (Teacher 7)

This statement supported the result of the study by Evans (2015), that emotional understanding and acceptance must be given value in handling SPED classes. Teachers who demonstrate emotional understanding are better equipped to empathize with their students' challenges, fostering a sense of belonging and trust. By recognizing and validating the emotions of their students, teachers can establish meaningful connections and build positive relationships, which are fundamental for effective teaching and learning. It is important for schools and educational institutions to provide professional development opportunities and support systems that focus on emotional understanding and coping strategies. By prioritizing the emotional well-being of teachers and students, SPED inclusive education program can thrive, enabling all students to reach their full potential and ensuring that every learner feels valued, supported, and included.

Conclusion

Based from the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Teachers handling learners with special educational needs in SPED inclusive education program have a significant impact on their learners. Teachers create an inclusive learning environment that maximize the potential of these learners and helps them, thrive academically and socially.
2. The use of positive reinforcement is a highly effective teaching strategy in SPED inclusive education program. It provides a supportive and motivating environment that enhances learning outcomes and fosters the overall development of students with diverse needs.
3. Teachers in SPED inclusive education program encounter various behavioral challenges, despite the challenges, teachers play a critical role in supporting students with behavioral difficulties. By employing a combination of patience, empathy, specialized training, collaboration, and ongoing professional development, teachers can create a positive and inclusive learning environment that fosters the social and academic growth of all learners.
4. Teachers can benefit from their own coping strategies to manage the demands and stressors associated with SPED inclusive education program.

The following is suggested in light of the findings:

1. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher advised school administrators to offer instructor support to help teachers overcome challenges in SPED inclusive education program.
2. Since the result of the findings shows that teachers encountered trouble in handling behavioral problems in SPED inclusive education program, teachers may receive training in inclusive teaching methods. It is necessary to give them professional development that focuses on identifying and assessing students with special needs, selecting the best teaching methods, and utilizing assistive technology and gadgets to promote learning.
3. Since the study reveals that there is lack of parental involvement, parents may encourage to actively assist their children's learning. Encourage parents to become more active and involved in the SPED inclusive education program, instructors and school administrators may decide to start conducting parent enhancement training.
4. Considering the results of the study, the researcher

developed the intervention program, which is advised for use in better executing SPED inclusive education programs for learners with special educational needs.

References

- Abushaira, M. (2012). Job satisfaction among special education teachers in Jordan. *International Interdisciplinary Journal of Education*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 48–56
- Ahmed, A. (2018). Perceptions of using assistive technology for students with disabilities in the classroom. *International Journal of Special Education*, 33, 129–139.
- Amor, A. M., Hagiwara, M. S., Shogren, K. A., Thompson, J. R., Verdugo, M. Á., Burke, K. M., & Aguayo, V. (2019). International perspectives and trends in research on inclusive education: a systematic review. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*.
- Antonova, I., Snezhko, Z., & Anohina, Y. (2019). The way we teach medical French using authentic audio-visual aids for exchange of experience. *Journal for the Education of Gifted Young Scientists*, 7(4), 953-965. <https://doi.org/10.17478/jegys.621922>
- Allam, F.C., & Martin, M.M. (2021). Issues and challenges in special education: A qualitative analysis from teacher's perspective. *Southeast Asia Early Childhood Journal*.
- Alquraini, A. (2012). Factors related to teachers' attitudes towards the inclusive education of students with severe intellectual disabilities in Riyadh, Saudi. *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 170–182
- Arcidiacono, F., and Baucal, A. (2020). Towards teacher professionalization for inclusive education: reflections from the perspective of the socio-cultural approach. *Eesti Haridusteaduste Ajakiri. Estonian J. Edu*.
- Benito, N.V., & Pangilinan, D.J.L. (2018). Inclusion of learners with special needs in the national assessment of the Philippines. UNESCO Bangkok.
- Bornman, J., & Donohue, D. (2013). South African Teachers' Attitudes toward Learners with Barriers to Learning: attention-deficit and hyperactivity disorder and little or no functional speech. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 85–104
- Bowker, A., Casas, J. F. (2016). What Parents Do When Children are Good: Parent Reports of Strategies for Reinforcing Early Childhood Prosocial Behaviors. Springer. 1310-1324
- Branstetter, R. (2020). How Teachers Can Help Students With Special Needs Navigate Distance Learning. Education.
- Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (2022). Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) 101.
- Creswell, J. (2013). Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches. Thousand Oaks. CA: Sage
- Davis, K. (2021). Teaching Special Education in the Midst of Covid-19: Current Conditions of Delivering Special Education Services during Distance Learning. Electronic Theses, Projects, and Dissertations, 1166

- Dano, J. & Arfasa, A. (2020). Primary school principals' readiness and qualification to implement inclusive education in western Oromia: Ethiopia. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 184–195
- Dapudong, R. C. (2014). Teachers' Knowledge and Attitude towards Inclusive Education: Basis for an Enhanced Professional Development Program. *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 4(4), 1. doi:10.5296/ijld.v4i4.6116
- Ehala, M. (2020). Tulevik on erikoolide päralt. [Future is for special schools]. Postimees.
- Ethenesh, A. (2017). Situational Analysis of Ethiopia. Unpublished report.
- Evans, J. (2015). 'What expert teachers do: Enhancing professional knowledge for classroom practice. *Professional Development in Education*, 37(4). <https://educapsycho.wordpress.com/2013/03/12/the-roleof-art/>
- Fadilah, M., Utari, P., & Wijaya, M. (2022). Government Communication in Implementing Inclusive Education for Working Towards the Sustainable Development Goals.
- FutureLearn (2021). What is inclusive education, and how can you implement it?
- Gaastra, G. F., Groen, Y., Tucha, L., & Tucha, O. (2016). The effects of classroom interventions on of task and disruptive classroom behavior in children with symptoms of attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder: A meta-analytic review. *PLoS ONE*, 11(2), e0148841–e0148841. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148841>.
- Gita-Carlos, R.A. (2022). PRRD OKs inclusive education for learners with disabilities. Philippine News Agency.
- Hlado, P., Dosedlová, J., Harvanková, K., et al. (2020). Workability among upper-secondary school teachers: examining the role of burnout, sense of coherence, and work-related and lifestyle factors. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 24, p. 9185
- Jones, B. F., Palincsar, A. S., Ogle, D. S., & Carr, E. G. (2017). Strategic teaching and learning: Cognitive instruction in the content areas. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development in cooperation with the North Central Regional Educational Laboratory. Kahler
- Kershner, R. (2017) Teaching children whose progress in learning is causing concern. In. D. Whitebread (ed.) *The Psychology of Teaching and Learning in the Primary School*. London: RoutledgeFalmer.
- Klassen, R. (2010). Teacher Stress: The mediating role of collective efficacy beliefs. *Journal of Educational Research*, 103, 342-350.
- Koller, D., Le Pouesard, M., and Rummens, J. A. (2018). Defining social inclusion for children with disabilities: A critical literature review. *Child. Soc.* 32, 1–13.
- Kupper, B., Õun, M., Tatmir, T., and Simso, T. (2020). Haridusinnovatsioon: kaasav haridus –kas oleme ikka kõigele mõelnud? [Educational innovation: Have we thought about everything?] Postimees.
- Leijen, A., Arcidiacono, F. & Baucal, A. (2021). The Dilemma of Inclusive Education: Inclusion for Some or Inclusion for All. *Front. Psychol.* 12:633066.
- Mackenzie, M.; Cologon, K. (2016). Embracing everybody: Approaching the inclusive early childhood education of a child labeled with autism from a social relational understanding of disability. *Autism Journal of Early Childhood*, 41(2).
- Mendoza, M. & Heymann, J. (2022). Implementation of Inclusive Education: A Systematic Review of Studies of Inclusive Education Interventions in Low- and Lower-Middle-Income Countries. *International Journal of Disability, Development, and Education*.
- Mngo, Z. Y., & Mngo, A. Y. (2018). Teachers' Perceptions of inclusion in a pilot inclusive education program: implications for instructional leadership. *Educational Research International*, vol. 13
- Mohanty, S. (2019). Exploring the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education at the elementary school level. *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 12, pp. 805–810
- Nishan, F. (2018). Challenges of Regular Teachers in Implementing Inclusive Education in Schools of Maldives
- Ng, S.W., & Kwan, Y.W. (2019). Inclusive Education Teachers—Strategies of Working Collaboratively With Parents of Children With Special Educational Needs in Macau. *International Journal of Educational Reform*, 29(3).
- Nilholm, C. (2020). Research about inclusive education in 2020 –

How can we improve our theories in order to change practice?.
European Journal of Special Needs Education

Nwosu, K., Wahl, W., Cassim H., Okwuduba, E., & Nnaemeka G.(2020).Teaching children with special needs in Nigerian regular classes: impact of gender, marital status, experience, and specialty. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, vol. 19, no. 12, pp. 86– 105

Murray-Harvey, R., Slee, P., Lawson, M., Silins, H., Banfield, G., & Russell, A. (2000). Under stress: The concerns and coping strategies of teacher education students. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 23(1)

Okeke, C., & Mazibuko, G.F. (2014). The Experiences Of Parents Of School Children With Special Education Needs: An Empirical Study. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*.

Reeves, P., Ng, S. L., Harris, M., & Phelan, S. K. (2020). The exclusionary effects of inclusion today: (Re)production of disability in inclusive education settings. *Disability & Society*.

Schuelka, M. J. s(2014). Constructing Disability in Bhutan: Schools, Structures, Policies and Global Discourse.

Schuelka, M. J., & Engsig, T. T. (2020). On the question of educational purpose: Complex educational systems analysis for inclusion. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 1–18.

Sesay, C. (2018). Teachers' Perceptions and Attitudes towards Inclusive Education in Sierra Leone. Doctoral Dissertation, Walden University, Minneapolis, Minnesota,

Singh, S., Kumar, S., & Singh, K. (2020). A study of attitude of teachers towards inclusive education. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 189–197

Taber, K. S. (2020). Mediated learning leading development the social development theory of Lev Vygotsky. In science education in theory and practice. Springer, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-43620-919>

Tonks, D., Kimmons, R., & Mason, S.L. (2021). Motivations among special education students and their parents for switching to an online school: Survey responses and emergent themes. *Online Learning*.

Urquhart C. (2013). Grounded Theory for Qualitative Research: A Practical Guide. <http://doi.org/10.4135/9781526402196>

Van de Wiel, N., Mattys, W., Cohen-Kettenis, P.C., and Van Engeland (2002). Effective treatments of school-aged conduct disordered children: Recommendations for changing clinical and research practices. *European Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 11, 79-84.

Waltz, M. (2016). The efficacy of a stress management and self-care training on student teachers' stress levels. PhD diss., Texas Tech University.

Yuwono, I., & Okech, J.B. (2021). The Classroom Impact of Trained Special Needs Education Teachers in Selected Schools: An Evaluation Study. *Front. Educ*.

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